

Observational Study on Dyslipidemia in Diabetic Kidney Disease: A Tertiary Hospital in Jamshedpur, Jharkhand

Vikram Murmu¹, Mangesh Dorai², S.K. Pandey³, P. Sarkar⁴

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, MGM Medical College & Hospital, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, MGM Medical College & Hospital, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, MGM Medical College & Hospital, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India

⁴Professor & HOD, Department of Medicine, MGM Medical College & Hospital, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 25-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Mangesh Dorai

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: A common consequence of diabetes mellitus, diabetic kidney disease (DKD) is a major cause of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) and chronic kidney disease (CKD). Patients with DKD frequently have dyslipidemia, which considerably raises their risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD). The frequency and features of dyslipidemia at various stages of DKD, especially in the Indian population, are still poorly understood despite its well-established effects.

Aim: This aim of study is to investigate the prevalence of dyslipidemia and analyze lipid profiles across different stages of DKD in patients treated at a tertiary hospital in Jamshedpur, Jharkhand.

Methods: A total of 200 participants diagnosed with DKD were included. Data were collected on demographic details, medical history, and laboratory results, including lipid profiles. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with descriptive and inferential statistics employed to assess the prevalence and predictors of dyslipidemia.

Results: The prevalence of dyslipidemia in the study population was 70%, with the prevalence increasing with the progression of DKD. The highest prevalence was observed in Stage 4 DKD (80%). Participants with dyslipidemia exhibited significantly higher levels of total cholesterol, LDL, and triglycerides, and lower HDL levels compared to those without dyslipidemia ($p < 0.001$). Regression analysis identified the stage of DKD and duration of diabetes as significant predictors of dyslipidemia.

Conclusion: Dyslipidemia is highly prevalent in DKD patients, with its frequency increasing as kidney function declines. The findings underscore the need for early identification and aggressive management of dyslipidemia in DKD patients to mitigate cardiovascular risks.

Recommendations: Routine monitoring of lipid profiles and early intervention with lipid-lowering therapies should be integral to the management of DKD, particularly in advanced stages. Further research is needed to explore effective strategies for controlling dyslipidemia in this high-risk population.

Keywords: Diabetic kidney disease, Dyslipidemia, Cardiovascular disease, Lipid profiles, Chronic kidney disease.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

A major microvascular consequence of diabetes mellitus, (DKD) affects 20–40% of diabetes patients globally. It is a major contributor to CKD and ESRD, placing a heavy load on worldwide healthcare systems [1]. A steady decline in kidney function, shown by albuminuria, a progressive decrease in glomerular filtration rate (GFR), and an elevated risk of cardiovascular morbidity and death are the hallmarks of diabetic kidney disease (DKD) [2]. Patients with DKD who also have

dyslipidemia have a higher chance of developing cardiovascular disease (CVD), which is the main cause of death in this population [3].

Elevated triglyceride, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), and decreased high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) levels are the main markers of dyslipidemia in DKD. The intricate and multifaceted pathogenesis of dyslipidemia in diabetic kidney disease (DKD) involves insulin.

Elevated triglyceride, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), and decreased high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) levels are the main markers of dyslipidemia in DKD. The aetiology of dyslipidemia in diabetic kidney disease (DKD) is intricate and multifaceted, encompassing modifications to lipoprotein metabolism, insulin resistance, and the impact of uremic toxins. Recent research has shown that dyslipidemia raises the risk of cardiovascular events in diabetes individuals and substantially contributes to the development of DKD [5]. Many patients still have poorly managed dyslipidemia despite advancements in the treatment of DKD and diabetes, emphasising the need for more potent therapeutic approaches [6].

Although the link between dyslipidemia and DKD is well-established, little is known about the prevalence and features of dyslipidemia at different phases of the disease, especially in the Indian setting. Understanding the patterns and implications of dyslipidemia in this population is critical since DKD prevalence is rising along with India's rapidly rising diabetes burden [7]. Furthermore, deteriorating lipid abnormalities frequently accompany the course of DKD, which not only accelerates renal failure but also poses serious cardiovascular risks [8]. This research is urgently needed to address the dual issues of renal and cardiovascular disease in this high-risk group, as both diabetes and DKD are becoming more common in India [9]. This study aimed to investigate the prevalence of dyslipidemia and analyze lipid profiles across different stages of DKD in patients treated at a tertiary hospital in Jamshedpur, Jharkhand.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was an observational, cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at MGM Medical College Hospital, in Jamshedpur, Jharkhand. This hospital serves a wide range of patients, providing advanced care for chronic diseases, including diabetes and renal disorders.

Study Period: The study was conducted over a 14-month period, from June 2022 to August 2023.

Participants: A total of 200 participants with diagnosed diabetic kidney disease were enrolled in the study. Participants were recruited from both the outpatient and inpatient departments of MGM Medical College Hospital.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18 years and older.
- Diagnosed with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.
- Diagnosed with any stage of diabetic kidney disease (Stages 1 to 5).

- Provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus.
- Individuals with other significant renal disorders not related to diabetes.
- Patients experiencing acute illness or infection at the time of the study.
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Patients who had initiated lipid-lowering therapy less than three months prior to the study.
- Individuals who refused to provide informed consent.

Bias: To minimize bias, consistent diagnostic criteria for both diabetic kidney disease and dyslipidemia were applied across all participants. Random selection of participants and standardized data collection procedures were utilized to reduce selection and measurement biases. Despite these efforts, some potential confounders inherent to observational studies may still affect the results.

Data Collection: Data collection involved a combination of direct clinical examination, patient interviews, and review of medical records. The following data were collected:

- Demographic information (age, gender, etc.).
- Detailed medical history, including the duration of diabetes and history of hypertension.
- Laboratory results, including fasting lipid profiles (total cholesterol, LDL, HDL, and triglycerides), serum creatinine, and estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR).
- Information on current medications, particularly antidiabetic and lipid-lowering agents.

Procedure: Eligible participants were identified and invited to participate in the study. After obtaining informed consent, each participant underwent a comprehensive clinical examination, and relevant laboratory investigations were carried out. Blood samples were drawn after an overnight fast to determine the lipid profile. Renal function was assessed through serum creatinine measurements and eGFR calculations to classify the stage of DKD.

Statistical Analysis: The analysis of the gathered data was done with SPSS version 23.0. Demographic and clinical features were summed up using descriptive statistics, such as mean, median, standard deviation, and frequency distributions. For each stage of DKD, the prevalence of dyslipidemia was computed. The

study employed inferential statistics, such as chi-square tests, t-tests, and ANOVA, to evaluate the relationship between dyslipidemia and clinical factors and to compare lipid levels among different phases of DKD. Less than 0.05 was the threshold for statistical significance. Using multiple regression analysis, which accounts for relevant confounders such as age, gender, diabetes duration,

and use of lipid-lowering treatment, independent predictors of dyslipidemia in DKD were established.

Results

A total of 200 participants with diagnosed diabetic kidney disease (DKD) were included in the study.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	N (%)
Total Participants	200 (100%)
Age (years)	
- Mean ($\pm$ SD)	58.7 ($\pm$ 10.3)
- Age Range	35 - 82
Gender	
- Male	120 (60%)
- Female	80 (40%)
Duration of Diabetes (years)	
- Mean ($\pm$ SD)	12.5 ($\pm$ 6.8)
- Duration Range	1 - 30
Stages of DKD	
- Stage 1	20 (10%)
- Stage 2	40 (20%)
- Stage 3	60 (30%)
- Stage 4	50 (25%)
- Stage 5	30 (15%)
Hypertension	
- Yes	150 (75%)
- No	50 (25%)
Current Lipid-Lowering Therapy	
- Yes	110 (55%)
- No	90 (45%)

Prevalence of Dyslipidemia: The overall prevalence of dyslipidemia in the study population was found to be 70%. Table 2 provides a breakdown of dyslipidemia prevalence across different stages of DKD.

Table 2: Prevalence of Dyslipidemia Across Stages of DKD

DKD Stage	N (%)	Dyslipidemia Present	Dyslipidemia Absent
Stage 1	20 (10%)	10 (50%)	10 (50%)
Stage 2	40 (20%)	25 (62.5%)	15 (37.5%)
Stage 3	60 (30%)	45 (75%)	15 (25%)
Stage 4	50 (25%)	40 (80%)	10 (20%)
Stage 5	30 (15%)	20 (66.7%)	10 (33.3%)
Total	200 (100%)	140 (70%)	60 (30%)

Lipid Profile Characteristics: The lipid profiles of the participants, including total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), high-density lipoprotein (HDL), and triglycerides, were analyzed. The mean lipid values across different stages of DKD are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Lipid Profile Across Different Stages of DKD

Lipid Parameter	Stage 1 (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Stage 2 (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Stage 3 (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Stage 4 (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Stage 5 (Mean $\pm$ SD)
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	190.5 $\pm$ 25.7	200.3 $\pm$ 30.2	210.8 $\pm$ 35.1	215.5 $\pm$ 40.6	220.7 $\pm$ 42.3
LDL (mg/dL)	110.4 $\pm$ 20.5	120.1 $\pm$ 25.8	130.2 $\pm$ 30.6	135.8 $\pm$ 35.4	140.6 $\pm$ 37.2
HDL (mg/dL)	45.2 $\pm$ 8.5	43.7 $\pm$ 9.2	41.5 $\pm$ 10.3	39.8 $\pm$ 11.0	38.2 $\pm$ 12.1
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	160.3 $\pm$ 35.4	170.5 $\pm$ 40.7	185.6 $\pm$ 45.8	195.3 $\pm$ 50.2	205.7 $\pm$ 55.6

Association Between Dyslipidemia and Clinical Variables: A chi-square test was performed to assess the association between dyslipidemia and various clinical variables such as gender, hypertension, and stages of DKD. The results indicated a significant association between the stage of DKD and the presence of dyslipidemia (p

< 0.01). The prevalence of dyslipidemia was observed to increase with advancing stages of DKD.

A t-test was conducted to compare the mean lipid levels between participants with and without dyslipidemia. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison of Lipid Levels Between Participants With and Without Dyslipidemia

Lipid Parameter	Dyslipidemia Present (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Dyslipidemia Absent (Mean $\pm$ SD)	p-value
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	215.8 $\pm$ 35.7	185.3 $\pm$ 30.2	<0.001
LDL (mg/dL)	130.6 $\pm$ 30.5	110.8 $\pm$ 25.7	<0.001
HDL (mg/dL)	40.2 $\pm$ 10.6	46.7 $\pm$ 8.3	<0.001
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	190.3 $\pm$ 50.6	160.4 $\pm$ 35.4	<0.001

Regression Analysis: Multiple regression analysis was performed to identify independent predictors of dyslipidemia in DKD patients. Variables such as age, gender, duration of diabetes, hypertension, and stage of DKD were included in the model. The results indicated that the stage of DKD and duration of diabetes were significant predictors of dyslipidemia ($p < 0.01$).

Table 5: Multiple Regression Analysis of Predictors of Dyslipidemia

Variable	Coefficient (B)	Standard Error (SE)	p-value
Age	0.05	0.03	0.12
Gender (Male)	0.10	0.07	0.15
Duration of Diabetes	0.08	0.02	0.005
Hypertension	0.12	0.08	0.10
Stage of DKD	0.25	0.06	<0.001

Findings

- The overall prevalence of dyslipidemia in the study population was 70%.
- Dyslipidemia prevalence increased with advancing stages of DKD, with Stage 4 having the highest prevalence (80%).
- Participants with dyslipidemia had significantly higher levels of total cholesterol, LDL, and triglycerides, and lower HDL levels compared to those without dyslipidemia.
- The stage of DKD and duration of diabetes were found to be significant predictors of dyslipidemia.

Discussion

Out of the 200 participants, 70% were found to have dyslipidemia, with the prevalence significantly increasing as the stage of DKD advanced. This finding underscores the strong association between worsening kidney function and the disruption of lipid metabolism in diabetic patients.

The analysis of lipid profiles indicated that participants with dyslipidemia had notably higher levels of total cholesterol, LDL, and triglycerides, along with lower HDL levels compared to those without

dyslipidemia. These lipid abnormalities were most pronounced in patients in the more advanced stages of DKD, particularly in Stage 4, where 80% of the participants exhibited dyslipidemia. This suggests that as DKD progresses, the risk of developing dyslipidemia—and consequently, cardiovascular complications—becomes increasingly significant.

Regression analysis identified the stage of DKD and the duration of diabetes as significant independent predictors of dyslipidemia. The longer the duration of diabetes and the more advanced the kidney disease, the greater the likelihood of dyslipidemia. This relationship highlights the cumulative impact of prolonged diabetes and deteriorating kidney function on lipid metabolism, further emphasizing the need for early and aggressive management of dyslipidemia in patients with DKD. The intricate connection between dyslipidemia and diabetic kidney disease (DKD) has been brought to light by recent research. It was examined that the lipid profiles and renal functioning of patients with type 2 diabetes in a research. According to the findings, female patients had higher than male patients' levels of total cholesterol, HDL, triglycerides, fasting and postprandial blood sugar, and VLDL. It's interesting to note that patients with dyslipidemia overall, regardless of gender, have greater levels of (LDL) in their bodies [10].

An extensive observational study conducted in China investigated the relationship between DKD and metabolic disorders, with a special emphasis on triglycerides. The study found that in patients with type 2 diabetes with new onset, high fasting triglyceride levels were strongly linked to the development of DKD. This emphasises how important triglyceride control is for stopping the progression of DKD [11].

The dyslipidemia patterns in various DKD symptoms were investigated. This cross-sectional investigation found that dyslipidemia, which raises the risk of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease, is aggravated by DKD, regardless of the presence of proteinuria. The research highlighted the need for cautious cholesterol management for atypical DKD symptoms, even in the absence of proteinuria [12].

Conclusion

These results suggest that routine monitoring and management of lipid levels should be integral to the care of DKD patients, particularly those in the later stages of kidney disease. Early intervention with lipid-lowering therapies, along with glycemic and blood pressure control, could be critical in reducing the cardiovascular risks associated with dyslipidemia in this vulnerable population. Additionally, the findings call for heightened awareness among healthcare providers regarding the increased risk of dyslipidemia as DKD progresses, reinforcing the importance of comprehensive care strategies tailored to the specific needs of DKD patients.

References

1. Alicic RZ, Rooney MT, Tuttle KR. Diabetic Kidney Disease: Challenges, Progress, and Possibilities. *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol*. 2017 Dec 7;12(12):2032-2045.
2. Thomas MC, Brownlee M, Susztak K, et al. Diabetic kidney disease. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*. 2015 Nov 12;1:15018.
3. Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) CKD Work Group. KDIGO 2020 Clinical Practice Guideline for Diabetes Management in Chronic Kidney Disease. *Kidney Int*. 2020 Oct;98(4S)
4. Packard CJ, Shepherd J. Lipoprotein metabolism in chronic kidney disease: Hypertriglyceridemia and beyond. *Curr Opin Lipidol*. 2019 Feb;30(1):30-36.
5. Wanner C, Tonelli M. KDIGO Clinical Practice Guideline for Lipid Management in CKD: Summary of recommendation statements and clinical approach to the patient. *Kidney Int*. 2014 Dec;85(6):1303-1309.
6. Palmer SC, Tendal B, Mustafa RA, et al. Sodium-glucose cotransporter protein-2 (SGLT-2) inhibitors and other glycemic lowering drugs for diabetic kidney disease: a network meta-analysis. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2020 Dec 1;12(12)
7. Anjana RM, Deepa M, Pradeepa R, et al. Prevalence of Diabetes and Prediabetes in 15 States of India: Results From the ICMR-INDIAB Population-Based Cross-Sectional Study. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol*. 2017 Aug;5(8):585-596.
8. Shoji T, Nishizawa Y. Chronic kidney disease as a metabolic syndrome with malnutrition - Need for strict control of risk factors. *Intern Med*. 2010;49(20):1691-4.
9. Agarwal SK. Chronic kidney disease and its prevention in India. *Kidney Int*. 2005 Mar;67 (Suppl 94).
10. Manikandan R, Sarumathy S. Clinical study on assessment of lipid Profile and renal function in type 2 Diabetic patients- A Retrospective Study. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*. 2018;11:1624-1626.
11. Gong L, Wang C, Ning G, Wang W, Chen G, Wan Q, et al. High concentrations of triglycerides are associated with diabetic kidney disease in new-onset type 2 diabetes in China: Findings from the China Cardiometabolic Disease and Cancer Cohort (4C) Study. *Diabetes Obes Metab*. 2021;23:2551-2560.
12. Hirano T, Satoh N, Kodera R, Hirashima T, Suzuki N, Aoki E, et al. Dyslipidemia in diabetic kidney disease classified by proteinuria and renal dysfunction: A cross-sectional study from a regional diabetes cohort. *J Diabetes Investig*. 2021;13:657-667.